

Study of the thermomechanical strain induced by current pulses in SiC-based Power MOSFET.

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Abstract— Power SiC-based MOSFETs are ongoing to substitute Si-based devices thanks to their significantly better performances that make them much suitable in power switching applications such as electric/hybrid vehicles. The increasingly widespread use of these devices in mission critical applications requires an ever-higher reliability, whereas the increase of the dissipated power during high-speed working cycling due to short current pulses leads to unavoidable thermal and mechanical stress. It has been demonstrated that, beside the temporal evolution of the temperature distribution, the mechanical stress localized on the metal layer play a key role in the product reliability. Here, we propose a direct method of measurement to evaluate the mechanical stress due to current pulses. This method highlights that the high Power SiC-based MOSFET undergoes to almost two different thermomechanical processes with completely different time scale. The obtained information allows constructing a link between the thermo-mechanical stress and the device failure conditions, with a special attention to the effects of the current pulses on the metal surface, as this is one of the weakness of the power devices. Used tools give us an almost complete characterization of the mechanical displacements of the metal and its time derivative (displacement rate) that may allow a more direct application of the Coffin Manson model to predict the mechanical fatigue lifetime, opening the way towards a simpler predictive model to evaluate the reliability.

Index Terms— Power MOSFET, Reliability, Silicon Carbide, Strain. Wide Band Gap semiconductors, Coffin Manson,

I. INTRODUCTION

WIDE Band Gap (WBG) semiconductors, such as Silicon Carbide (SiC) and Gallium Nitride (GaN), thanks to their capability to work at higher temperatures, voltages and frequencies, push the research to improve the devices that are already commercially available since the begun of the century. In the last decade, a special attention has been spent to the SiC-based devices that largely outperform the silicon-based ones and find applications in many fields of power electronics, especially in energy conversion and automotive world [1;2;3;4]. 6th generation SiC-SBDs (Schottky Barrier Diode) are today available, alongside MOSFETs, JFETs, and Hybrid SiC-IGBT modules. Due to the wide spreading of the application fields, these devices are increasingly used in mission critical application, hence a deeper comprehension of their failure mechanisms and a more complete and suitable modeling for reliability assessment is needed. Due to its higher stiffness compared to silicon, the power cycling capability of SiC devices is particularly crucial [5][6]. The cyclic quick increasing of temperature during high current pulses leads to both thermal and, consequently, mechanical stress, that wears out the gate oxide layer, the metal and the bonding [7;8;9]. In this frame, the reliability becomes more challenging to evaluate, specially taking into account that the modern devices technology has shifted towards ultra-thin body transistors and high thermal conductivity materials. In these devices, the crowding of carriers along a confined dimension [10] not only creates local hotspots but also give rise to mechanical stress among the layers. Hence, the study of deformation mechanisms and the relationship between temperature and failure

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mechanisms could provide key information to improve reliability modeling and prediction. In the last years, many experimental techniques and theoretical simulations have been proposed in order to measure micrometric mechanical deformations and cracks, such as: Digital Image Correlation (DIC) method [11], Finite Element Analysis [12], Shearography [13]. The industry qualification of the devices is based on the reliability prediction that relies on the well know statistical methods based on the Coffin Manson model that defines the number of actual failures occurring as a fraction of the total number of units subjected to an accelerated test [14,15]. In addition, to a statistical analysis of the electronic device failure issues, it is also useful to make a qualitative analysis of failures, in order to identify product weaknesses caused by flaws in the product's design or manufacturing process. In any case, the temperature values and its distribution during the operation of the electronic device is a key parameter. It has been demonstrated that repeated high current pulses lead to a quick temperature increasing and, consequently, to a rapid mechanical displacement of the surface metal layer of the device under test (DUT) [6,7]. The out-of-plane mechanical displacement can be evaluated without decapsulating the DUT, hence observing it in its real working conditions [16]. The above the above phenomena become very important in automotive applications where the frequencies involved are of the order of a few KHz, for example in applications such as gasoline or diesel injection, or power management in electric engine. In these cases, the strain mechanisms and the thermal behavior are fast enough to follow the current pulses and give rise to cumulative effects of mechanical stress.

In this paper, we focus on the strain mechanisms involved during the power cycling and demonstrate that at kHz pulses frequencies the DUT undergoes to almost two different thermomechanical processes both of them to be taken into account for a more precise lifetime estimation. Thermal and mechanical measurements are performed during operation of DUT by using non-invasive techniques based on emission microscopy technique in the infrared range and on the optical interferometry, respectively. The surface metal layer of the stressed DUT has been characterized by means the Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) in order to highlight the morphological damages induced by the thermo-mechanical strain.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

The analyzed DUT is a Power MOSFET based on silicon carbide technology provided by ST Microelectronics. Before the thermal and mechanical characterization, the DUT has been decapsulated, removing the resin on the top of the metal layer. The exposure of the metal layer needs to detect the thermal evolution of the DUT during its operation and it allows performing the mechanical measurements in the same conditions and to compare the metal surface before and after the failure of the DUT. Its performance has been studied in Terminal Short Circuit (TSC) configuration (see Fig. 1), which is one of the overload conditions that are commonly used to test the roughness of the automotive devices [17]. Through the V_{in}

voltage, DUT is activated for a fixed ton time interval ($t_{on} = 5$ ms) and it is switched off for $t_{off} = 1.5$ s. For each V_{in} pulse, the peak current value is 80 A with $V_{DS} = 10$ V and $V_{GS} = 15$ V.

Figure 1: a) electric configuration for TSC (Terminal Short Circuit) overload test; b) optical image of the decapsulated DUT.

Thermal measurements have been performed by a high-speed emission microscope working in the infrared range. The experimental setup is described elsewhere [18]. The system is able to record time resolved thermal maps with an equivalent frame rate of 1200000 images/s, hence it is able to catch the thermal events due to very short current pulses. Out-of-plane mechanical displacements have been measured by a microscope-based vibrometer (Polytec, MSA-500). The Laser-Doppler vibrometer works on the basis of optical interference of two coherent laser beams with intensities I_1 and I_2 . The resulting intensity is not just the sum of the single intensities, but it is modulated according to the formula:

$$I = I_1 + I_2 + 2\sqrt{I_1 I_2} \cos[2\pi(r_1 - r_2)/\lambda]$$

$$I_{Max} = I_1 + I_2 + 2\sqrt{I_1 I_2}$$

$$I_{Min} = I_1 + I_2$$

Figure 2: simplified scheme of the interferometric setup: the current pulses are driven by a controller that synchronizes the acquisition data and control scan the beam along the mesh.

A displacement of the object under investigation ($r_1 = r(t)$) generates the slipping of the dark and bright (fringe) pattern

typical of interferometry. An acousto-optic modulator (AOM) is inserted in the reference optical path to detect the displacement direction.

One complete dark-bright cycle on the detector corresponds to an object displacement of exactly half of the wavelength of the light used, therefore the instrument allows to detect the sub micrometric displacement that occurs at the metal surface of the DUT due to the current pulses. Synchronizing the current pulses with the acquisition it is possible to record point by point the time resolved displacement of the surface. Designing a suitable grid of points, the system will produce a matrix data and, after a software interpolation, the deformation over time as a movie may be build. The final maximum allowed lateral and vertical resolution for the displacement acquisition depend on the objective magnification. The instrument has been equipped with a 100X objective and performs a lateral resolution of about 500nm and a vertical resolution of about 25nm. AFM measurements have been performed in semi-contact mode using a Si-cantilever mounted on an NT-MDT mod. SMENA microscope.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3a shows the thermal map of the DUT acquired at 5 ms after the current pulse started, also corresponding to the instant when the temperature reaches its maximum

Figure 3: a) thermal map acquired at 5 ms after the current pulse. b) temperature behavior versus time acquired at the hottest point of the metal surface.

The thermal map shows that the temperature reaches its maximum at the center of the DUT, near to the bonding wire area. Figure 3b describes the temporal evolution of the temperature acquired at the hottest point on the metal surface. The temperature does not exceed 80°C in the above defined working conditions. Figure 4a shows the surface displacement frozen at the end of the current pulse. The displacement map is characterized by a maximum displacement placed at the center of the device, where the temperature reaches its highest value. Figure 4b reports the displacement trend vs time, acquired in the point marked in Figure 4a. Interestingly, the displacement shows a narrow peak when the current pulse occurs, after the end of the current pulse, the metal comes back near to the zero position and a slow displacement starts. For a better understanding of the stress undergoes the DUT, we repeated the experiment exciting the DUT with a burst consisting of three current pulses at a frequency of 100Hz. The current pulses train is a regime very close to the real working situation hence this condition can provide more information on possible cumulative damage effects on the DUT surface.

Figure 4: mechanical deformations of DUT during its operation in TSC configuration: (a) maximum displacement acquired at 5ms; (b) temporal evolution of displacement at the center of the DUT (considered point is marked in figure 4a) acquired for 1s.

Each pulse was 5ms wide with a duty cycle of 50%. The three pulses have been obtained by a 0.16 F capacitor; hence they have a decreasing peak current, and precisely of 85A, 80A and 75 A. The temporal evolution of the DUT surface displacement

during the current train collected at the position, where the temperature reaches its maximum, is showed in Figure 5. Initially, the surface displacement follows the current pulses amplitude, and ranges between $1,6 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{m}$ to $1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{m}$ as the current peaks decrease from 85A to 75A. After each pulse, the displacement goes back, but never reaching the starting point. After the current train end, a slow displacement of the entire surface is observed.

Figure 5 Displacement of the DUT surface during the current train, collected near to the solder joint where the temperature reaches its maximum.

The temporal evolution of the DUT surface displacement during the current train collected at the position, where the temperature reaches its maximum, is showed in Figure 5. Initially, the surface displacement follows the current pulses amplitude, and ranges between $1,6 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{m}$ to $1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{m}$ as the current peaks decrease from 85A to 75A. After each pulse, the displacement goes back, but never reaching the starting point. After the current train end, a slow displacement of the entire surface is observed. These findings suggest that, during the pulse current cycling, the DUT undergoes two rather different processes: at first, a quick strain that mainly involves the metal and presumably the first layers of semiconductor affecting the solder joint too; subsequently, a displacement that involves the whole device is observed, which is related to the slow heat diffusion related to the power dissipation inside the semiconductor that produces an increasing of the temperature of the entire chip and consequently to a thermal expansion. The above observation let us conclude that, during the normal operation, the DUT temperature will increase its baseline reaching a mean value. At operational frequencies of the order of hundreds of Hz, the temperature quickly increases following the current pulses and reaching a value far beyond the one measured with standard systems such as thermal cameras. Moreover, despite the relative low value reached by the temperature during the current pulses, the quick displacement induces a cumulative stress on the metal that, together with the slow surface movement, must be taken into account for a more complete estimation of the lifetime.

Figure 6: Optical images of the DUT surface close to the bonding area acquired with a magnification of 10X before (a) and after (b) the stress.

During the above reported test, the investigated DUT undergoes to approximately 21500 current pulses, after which the DUT is failed. Figure 6 shows the optical image of the DUT surface, after the failure. Noticeably, the optical image acquired with a magnification of 10X clearly shows a stressed area at the center of the DUT, which appears blackened. A greater magnification allows seeing the detail of the damages of the metal surface: close to the gate contact, the metal layer is still intact with a smooth surface; on the contrary, the central area of the DUT is characterized by a higher roughness.

These observations are directly correlated to the thermo-mechanical analysis, confirming that the area that reaches the maximum temperature values and that is affected by the maximum mechanical displacement will fail. The contact metallization conventionally consists of a vacuum-deposited aluminum layer, characterized by a grains structure. Due to the difference in thermal expansion between the semiconductor and the aluminum, we can foresee that the metal layer will suffer a considerable stress if repeated temperature swings occur. Thus, the metallization layer is subjected to a compressive stress during the heating phase of temperature cycles. Literature distinguishes two different temperature regimes [19]: high temperature (above 175°C), in this case diffusional creep and plastic deformation involving conservative motion of

dislocations are assumed as; low temperature (below 175°C), when the main mechanism of mass transport is the plastic deformation caused by the compressional fatigue. The plastic deformation can lead to the extrusion of single grains. This process leads to an increasing surface roughness of the metallization with the macroscopic observable effect of a dull non-reflective surface appearance. In the cooling phase of the temperature cycle, tensile stress can lead to cavitation effects at the grain boundaries if the elastic regime is exceeded.

Figure 7: (a) AFM image (scan size $80 \mu\text{m} \times 80 \mu\text{m}$) of the good area (close to the gate contact) and measured average roughness; (b) AFM image (scan size $80 \mu\text{m} \times 80 \mu\text{m}$) of the stressed area (close to the drain contact) and measured average roughness. Histogram of the grains radius distribution calculated (c) in the good area and (d) in the stressed area of the DUT metallization.

This can lead to an increase in electrical resistance of the surface metallization. In our case, the DUT is subjected to tens of thousands operating cycles in TSC configuration. In the chosen operating conditions, the DUT is affected by repetitive thermo-mechanical cycles that activate the reconstruction of metallization. Since the maximum achieved temperature (about 80°C, see Fig. 3) is well below of the threshold 175°C, we attribute the cause of the reconstruction of metallization to the mechanical fatigue of the metal layer. The relatively low number of cycles after which the DUT fails highlights that the strain/strain rate ratio acts as a very high efficiency acceleration factor.

Figure 7 shows the AFM images (scan size $80 \mu\text{m} \times 80 \mu\text{m}$) and the distribution of the radius of the metal grains measured in the good and in the stressed region. The average roughness of the metal surfaces is reported inside the AFM images. The AFM analysis and the calculated roughness agree with the previous analyses: the average roughness increases from about 190 nm, in the good region, to 292 nm in the stressed region. This variation, of about 100 nm, of the surface average roughness is linked to the variation of the metal grains size. Assuming that each grain has an almost circular shape, Fig. 7 c-d show the histograms of the grain radius distribution calculated in the both analyzed regions. In the good region (see Fig. 7c), the histogram is characterized by a narrow band

centered at 0.8 μm, with a shoulder at lower values. On the contrary, in the stressed region the histogram is characterized by a flat and large band, slightly shifted towards higher values of the radius size. The increase of the metal roughness is related to an increase of the grains size and confirms the grains reconstruction process of metallization, which leads to a progressive damage of the metal contact, until the DUT failure.

IV. CONCLUSION

V. In conclusion, the high-speed thermal maps confirm that the SiC based DUT, with the same power dissipated, operates at lower temperatures than the case of silicon counterparts ensuring a better reliability [20]. The time resolved mechanical displacement maps allow, at the best of our knowledge, for the first time to identify two different processes that affect the device during its cycle of operation: a fast process engaging the metallization and the first layers of the DUT and a slow process due to the to heat diffusion involving the whole device [21]. The fast process is the main responsible of the metal damage, hence the displacement and strain-rate must be taken into account as a key factor in a predictive Coffin Manson model to obtain a more realistic evaluation of the lifetime.

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